

**ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ ОСНОВНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ
ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КОМПАНИИ ALIBABA НА ОСНОВЕ МЕТОДОВ
МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКОГО МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ**

**FORECASTING THE MAIN FINANCIAL INDICATORS OF ALIBABA
BASED ON MATHEMATICAL MODELING METHODS**

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Целью данного исследования является анализ и прогноз финансовых показателей предприятия Alibaba с помощью математической модели для прогнозирования бизнес-ситуации предприятия в последние годы, и на основе этого анализ сильных и слабых сторон предприятия и предложение улучшений в бизнес-стратегии предприятия.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and predict the financial indicators of Alibaba enterprise by using mathematical model, to calculate the operating situation of the enterprise in recent years, and to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the enterprise on this basis. Suggestions for improvement of the business strategy of the enterprise are put forward.

Ключевые слова: *метод математического моделирования, многомерная линейная регрессионная модель, финансовые показатели, деловая ситуация, прогнозирование, оптимизация, развитие.*

Key words: *mathematical modeling method, multivariate linear regression model, financial indicators, operating condition, prediction, optimization, development.*

In the current stock market, the main goal of the listed company is to ensure the maximum benefit of the listed company and to ensure that the stakeholders of the listed company achieve the maximum benefit. To achieve these goals, the stock price of the listed company needs to maintain a long-term and stable growth. And the operating condition of listed company is the long-term and important factor that determines its stock price. The operating condition of listed companies is reflected by financial statements. Therefore, the analysis and study of the financial indicators in the financial statements can quickly control the operating condition of the listed company, and put forward suggestions for the future sustainable development [1].

In this paper, multivariate linear regression model method and the financial indicators analysis method in the mathematical model to construct the model of the financial indicators and the operating condition, so as to predict its future development trend [2].

The relevance of this topic is the use of mathematical models for quantitative analysis of the company's operating conditions and financial indicators. Different from the analysis of business situation through management strategy, industry situation and macroeconomic situation, the mathematical model analysis not only simplifies the analysis process, but also is more intuitive, and provides an intuitive data for the future development.

Financial indicators analysis refers to the analysis indicators that summarizes and evaluates the financial situation and operating results of an enterprise, including solvency indicator, operating ability indicator, profitability indicator and development ability indicator [3].

Solvency refers to the enterprise's ability to repay the due debts (including principal and interest). It is an important symbol to measure the current financial ability of enterprises, especially the liquidity of floating assets. Short-term solvency analysis mainly adopts ratio analysis method, the measurement indicators mainly has current ratio.

The current ratio is the ratio of current assets to current liabilities, which indicates how many current assets per yuan of current liabilities are used as the guarantee of repayment, which reflects the ability of current assets to repay current liabilities. The formula is: $\text{Current ratio} = \text{current assets} / \text{current liabilities}$

Under general circumstances, the higher the current ratio, the stronger the enterprise short-term solvency, because the higher the ratio, not only reflects that the enterprise has more working capital to offset the short-term debt, but also shows that the amount of assets the enterprise can realize is large, the smaller the risk of creditors.

In theory, it is reasonable to maintain the current ratio at 2:1. However, because of the nature of the industry, the actual standard of current ratio is also different. Therefore, when analyzing the current ratio, we should compare it with the average current ratio of the same industry and the historical current ratio of the enterprise, so as to draw a reasonable conclusion.

Operating ability analysis refers to the analysis of its asset utilization efficiency through calculating the relevant indicators of the enterprise capital turnover, and is the analysis of the enterprise management management level and asset application ability. The main indicators are total asset turnover.

Total assets turnover rate is the ratio of the net income of the main business to the total assets. It can be used to reflect the efficiency of the use of all assets of an enterprise. The formula is: $\text{Total assets turnover} = \text{net operating income} / \text{average total assets}$

The total asset turnover reflects the efficiency of the use of all assets of an enterprise. The high turnover rate indicates that the operating efficiency of all assets is high and the income obtained is much; the low turnover rate indicates that the operating efficiency of all assets is low and the income obtained is less, which will eventually affect the profitability of the enterprise.

Profitability is the ability to increase enterprise capital appreciation, which is usually reflected in the size and level of enterprise income amount. The measurement indicators are mainly return on equity.

Return on equity, which refers to the ratio of net profit to equity in a certain period of time. It can reflect the ability of investors to invest in their own capital to obtain net income, that is, relationship between investment and reward, so it is the core indicator to evaluate the efficiency of enterprise capital management. The formula is: $\text{Return on equity} = \text{net profit} / \text{equity} \times 100\%$

The return on equity is the most comprehensive and representative indicator to evaluate the level of enterprise's own capital and its accumulated remuneration, which reflects the comprehensive benefit of enterprise's capital operation. This indicator has strong, wide range of application, not limited by the industry. In the comprehensive ranking of the performance of listed companies in

China, this indicator ranks first. Through the comprehensive comparative analysis of this indicator, we can see the position of enterprise profitability in the same industry and the difference level with similar enterprises. It is generally believed that the higher the return on equity, the stronger the ability of the enterprise's own capital to obtain income, the better the operating benefit, and the higher the degree of protection to the investors and creditors of the enterprise.

Development ability is the potential ability of enterprises to expand scale and strengthen strength on the basis of survival. Measurement indicator are mainly total assets year-on-year growth rate.

The year-on-year growth rate of total assets is the ratio of the total assets growth of the enterprise this year to the total assets at the beginning of the year, which reflects the growth of the assets scale of the enterprise in the current period. The formula for calculating the year-on-year growth rate of total assets is:

year-on-year growth rate of total assets = Total asset growth this year / Total assets at the beginning of the year $\times 100\%$

The higher the growth rate of total assets indicates that the faster the expansion within a certain period of time. However, in the analysis, it is necessary to pay attention to the quality and quantity relationship of the asset scale expansion, as well as the follow-up development ability of the enterprise, to avoid blind expansion.

Table 1. Dynamics of key financial indicators of «Alibaba» for 2012 - 2019 [6].

indicators	Years							
	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
current ratio	1.8	1.81	3.58	2.58	1.95	1.89	1.3	1.91
total asset turnover (times)	0.62	0.6	0.42	0.33	0.36	0.41	0.45	0.45
return on equity (%)	40.6	92.8	26.11	39.32	17.5	19.7	20.25	23.65
year-on-year growth in total assets (%)	35.11	74.88	128.99	42.68	39.14	41.5	34.58	36.05

It can be seen from the above table that in 2012 to 2019, although the current ratio of Alibaba has fluctuated, it is basically higher than the industry level and maintained at about 2, indicating that Alibaba has strong short-term solvency and small risk of creditors, which is conducive to future debt issuance; Alibaba's turnover rate of total assets is "u" type, indicating that the turnover rate of total assets has increased in recent years, the operating efficiency of all assets has been relatively improved, and the income has increased; Alibaba's return on equity showed a continuous downward trend, although rising in recent years, but the rise is not large, reflecting Alibaba's declining profitability in the same industry due to the increase of competitors in the industry; Although the year-on-year growth rate of Alibaba's operating revenue fluctuates greatly, it is both positive and high growth rate. Alibaba's product market prospect is good and has not yet faced the risk of product renewal.

After analyzing the financial indicators, a multi linear regression model for Alibaba's business status and financial indicators was constructed to predict the future business development.

Table 2. Dynamics of operating conditions of «Alibaba» for 2012 - 2019 [6].

years	operation revenue(billion yuan)	Year-on-year growth in operating income(%)	operation cost(billion yuan)	Year-on-year growth in operating costs(%)	net profit(billion yuan)	Year-on-year growth in net profit (%)
2012	34.52	/	9.72	/	8.65	/
2013	52.50	52.11	13.37	37.56	23.40	170.59
2014	76.20	45.14	23.83	78.28	24.32	3.92
2015	101.14	32.73	34.36	44.14	71.29	193.13
2016	158.27	56.48	59.48	73.14	41.23	-42.17
2017	250.27	58.12	107.04	79.96	61.41	48.96
2018	376.84	50.58	206.93	93.31	80.23	30.65
2019	509.71	35.26	282.37	36.46	140.35	74.93

Let the dependent variable be y , k independent variable $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k$, describe how the y of the dependent variable depends on the $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k$ of the independent variable and the ε of the error term is called the multivariate regression model. Its general form may be expressed as:

$$y = B_0 + B_1x_1 + B_2x_2 + \dots + B_kx_k + \varepsilon$$

$B_0, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_k$ is the parameter of the model ; ε is the error term.[5]

The regression equation of Year-on-year growth in operating income is :

$$Y_1 = 154.1505 - 37.97895X_1 - 160.8805X_2 + 0.0779X_3 + 0.7265X_4$$

The regression equation of Year-on-year growth in operating costs is:

$$Y_2 = 334.6771 - 85.9351X_1 - 420.1939X_2 - 0.2696X_3 + 1.8208X_4$$

Then, the regression equation of Year-on-year growth in net profit is:

$$Y_3 = -360.4589 + 164.477X_1 + 469.5364X_2 + 2.6993X_3 - 3.8491X_4$$

where x_1 - current ratio;

x_2 - Total assets turnover (times);

x_3 - Return on equity(%);

x_4 - Year-on-year growth in total assets(%).

So, we have the following results.

The financial indicators of the enterprise is closely related to the operating condition. Strengthening the current ratio, the turnover rate of total assets and the return rate of net assets can make the operating cost of the enterprise decrease from the same period last year, thus increasing the growth rate of net profit from the same period last year.

To promote future net profit growth, we should maintain the above three indicators of stable growth. The increase of the current ratio indicates that the short-term liquidity of the enterprise is enhanced, but the excessive current ratio will also affect the profitability of the enterprise. Therefore, it can be concluded that the current ratio of Alibaba will be in a stable and effective state at present and in the future. The increase of total asset turnover rate can reflect the improvement of enterprise's sales ability, and the increase of enterprise's sales will accelerate the turnover of assets and bring about the increase of absolute profit. The return on net assets reflects the profitability of the enterprise, the return on investment activities and the efficiency of the use of shareholder funds.

Although the year - on - year growth rate of total assets is negatively correlated to the year - on - year growth rate of net profit , the growth rate of total assets reflects the future development ability of the enterprise , so it cannot ignore the year - on - year growth rate of total assets for profit

growth . Only by ensuring the sustainable development of the enterprise can the future profit growth of the enterprise ensure.

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